

Digital Library and Information Technology

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Abstract:

Today's era is the era of information technology and technology is advancing a lot in the present world. In such a situation it is imperative that we stay updated and for that we must maintain the latest improvements in technology so that we can perform our work efficiently and accurately without any problem. Computer literacy has increased with the development of science and technology. A lot of research in the field of technology has led to the emergence of new technologies. By using this new technology, there is a drastic change in the library sector. The library sector is not behind in this. In a developing country like India, the government has implemented a digital literacy campaign in every village. In this article we will briefly learn about digital library and information technology.

Introduction:

Digital library is also known as online library and internet library. The most special thing about digital library is that the reader can use it from any corner of the world. Although more and more people of the country are attracted towards this sector, the most important thing is to bring digital library to every citizen. Students can access digital library anywhere with the help of internet. Digital libraries have unlimited space than any physical library. This library will have almost all books from around the world available in digital form, which can be accessed from any location. Students will not need to go anywhere and register for the book, but students will be able to read the books of their choice at home.

A library is generally a place where all types of printed materials as well as manuscripts are kept together. Readers, reading materials and staff are three important components of a library. The basic purpose of a library is to store knowledge and information. These tools can be taken from the library for use and returned for a limited period of time. In modern times, the concept of libraries has changed and it has become an information exchange institution. Currently, in the era of digital and information technology, audio-visual media is also seen in the library. The new library format is becoming computerized. It is possible to search for information on the Internet. Today the concept of digital library has come all over the world. With the digital library students will have almost all the books from around the world in digital form which can be read and viewed by the readers from any place. With digital library, students can read books at home instead of going anywhere to get books.

Digitization of Libraries need have Time:

Libraries have a centuries-old tradition of maintaining a collection of books. As human life changes with time. Also, this change is taking place in the library. Libraries have started moving in that direction by adapting to technology. Today the

concept of digital library has come all over the world with the help of digital library it is possible for you to read many valuable books from all over the world from the library, not only that but anyone can register as a member of that library and provide the facility of the desired method. Through 'E-Library', students will be able to get help in getting educational books, various sources of educational curriculum, and documents with latest and latest technology information, e-books, e-journals, scientific journals in a short period of time. Today, all libraries are being transformed into 'Global Knowledge Centers'. Computerization is its first step. The emphasis is on digitalization of all libraries for better future of libraries. Various software are used for information and preservation of library resources. It is mainly used in college. Now the use of computer has increased in all fields. The benefit from it is attracting everyone. Therefore digitization of libraries has become the need of the hour.

What is digital library?

A digital library is a collection of digital assets. Those who do not have any physical existence. As the name suggests, a digital library is a library where books exist in digital or electronic form. These books can be accessed only with the help of electronic devices. Digital library is also known as online library and internet library. The most special thing about digital library is that the reader can use it from any corner of the world. Although more and more people of the country are attracted towards this sector, the most important thing is to bring digital library to every citizen. Students can access digital library anywhere with the help of internet. Digital libraries have unlimited space than any physical library. In this library, almost all the books of the world will be available in digital form, which can be viewed and read from any location.

Advantages of Digital Library:

Free Educational Resources provides visitors with numerous resources like educational materials, training, courses, scientific publications, etc. Not only do public libraries provide their services face-to-face, some of them have also integrated e-learning.

Digital library saves space and time. Less manpower is required and hence cost savings. Rare historical texts, literature may be available. Also, materials in different formats can be saved. For generosity. Texts, periodicals, bibliographies, printed non-bibliographic material apart from non-print non-bibliographic material for free. Sound recording, currency picture, video footage etc.

1. A reader can access digital information through internet at home.
2. A digital library can be handled 24 hours and 365 days a year.
3. The same information can be read by many readers simultaneously through digital library.
4. A digital library can store more information than a traditional library.
5. Reader can give time as per his convenience.
6. Readers can acquire knowledge with the help of library staff and digital media.

Disadvantages of digital library:

1. Digital libraries can be a bit technically complex.
2. Digitization may violate copyright laws. Because one author's ideas can be used by another author without his prior consent.
3. As more computers are connected to the Internet, they slow down and waste more time for the user.
4. Reading material in digital library cannot be read without media. For generosity. Computer, Mobile.
5. Internet facility is not available everywhere.

Purpose of Digital Library:

Today the concept of digital library has come all over the world with the help of digital library it is possible for you to read many valuable books from all over the world from the library, not only that but anyone can register as a member of that library and provide the facility of the desired method.

Digital reading materials are stored, archived and displayed using computers. Information is stored and retrieved through digitization of information. Also, the purpose of digital library is to create database in the form of CDs, to provide computerized books.

Information Technology and its Components:

Information technology is the collection, storage, processing and communication of information. The term information technology is synonymous with telematics, informatics. The

Information Technology Act 2000 defines information- Information as includes information, original text, images, sounds, symbols, computer program systems and base information sets.

Information technology is used in library management, library computerization, library networking, transcription services and technical communication. The concept of information technology is formed by the combination of all the elements like collection of information, edition, photo technology, computer artificial intelligence, hardware etc. In general, information technology is developed by coordinating computer software, networking, internet, messaging, information retrieval and storage.

Importance of Information Technology in Libraries:

Along with imparting knowledge to the readers, it is important to develop the library with the help of various technologies. Nowadays, new technology has made it possible to convey more information to the readers in less time. Schools were closed for the past two years due to the Corona epidemic. In between, only classes 10th - 12th were running from time to time. The entire academic year 2020-21 has been taught online. One session of the year 2021-22 was taught online. Due to the development of information technology, the learning days of the students in the corona era have not been wasted. Today, many libraries are offering home-based services to readers. By using WhatsApp technology, libraries are providing their readers with the information they want without delay. Through the information technology network, one library can exchange information with another library. Information technology allows readers to send information they want via e-mail, fax, or other links. In the future, the existing functions of the libraries will remain the same. But all libraries must take the help of technology. This super highway of information technology includes computer networks, telephone, and wireless. Every field is progressing because of the World Wide Web. The world is interconnected because of the web. Finding information was a very time-consuming process. But today, due to technology, information is available within a short time.

Library Network:

Inflibnet is an important organization working under the University Grants Commission i.e. UGC like Ayuka in Pune. The full name of this organization is 'Information and Library Network'. University Grants Board established Information and Library Network (Inflibnet) in 1991. This institute is located in Gandhinagar, Gujarat. This organization is working in the field of higher education in various works such as helping universities in India in research work, providing

guidance for quality research, providing e-resources, preparing a unified table of books available in university libraries in India. An important objective is to create a chain of libraries and information centers, important national institutions, research and development institutions with the help of this network. Also, the basic objective of this network is to make the available resources of libraries in the country accessible to all. In this, Delnet, a network of metropolitan areas, includes information sets of books, information sets of multilingual books, e-mail services, group list of current periodicals, information from abroad, and online research of collections.

Library Mechanization:

Electronic devices are used for mechanization of library. Library mechanization is the use of machines for repetitive work, clerical work and library services. Libraries are responsible for catering to the information needs of readers. Libraries also have to change the format of information transmission to meet the changing needs of the readers. Electronic devices are being used for mechanization of library. At present, continuous study and research is going on technical and scientific subjects. A lot of information is published on new research. Libraries are also having to change their book-centered approach as per need and time. It has changed from a book-centric perspective to an information-centric one. So today many libraries are mechanized. As mechanization has affected various spheres of life. Similarly, the use of e-books, e-magazines has started in the library sector today.

Advantages of Information Technology:

In the twenty-first century, information technology has become an integral part of our lives. Information technology is proving to be a boon to the world. From children to elderly grandparents, from waking up in the morning to going to bed at night, technology devices are being used everywhere. Information technology has completely changed human life. Today, information technology is used in many places. Information technology has played an important role in the days of global epidemics such as mobile, internet, business and today's corona. Traffic on the roads reduced, schools and colleges were closed, and exams were cancelled, but in all these things went smoothly due to information technology. Even though schools are closed, children are being educated using information technology. Online exams are being conducted. Government and administration are performing their responsibility and duties properly by using information technology. Information technology is helping to make things easier.

Technology has brought the world closer together. Through technology we can share information all over the world. Technology saves time and money. Information technology plays an important role in the growth of any country's economy. Many companies are doing business with the help of technology and due to this, employment has been made available to the unemployed.

Summary:

The present age is the digital age. The development of information technology has been very beneficial during the infectious disease of Covid-19. In reality, schools and colleges were closed, but students were in the flow of education due to information technology. Today, the concept of digital library is becoming popular everywhere. Information technology is being widely used in libraries. Information technology has become the need of the age in all fields such as educational, social, political, and cultural. Advances in all areas like education, entertainment, information acquisition, communication, transportation, health, etc., have improved the physical life of human beings due to the growth of information technology. Technology has made human work easier. But it is necessary to be careful. How do we use technology? Everything depends on it.

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